

A Study on Consumer Behavior Using it Model (Engel-Kollat-Blackwell Model)

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Abstract

Consumers are the core of marketing. They only buy product that they strongly desire. To understand the needs of the consumer you need to understand the behaviour of the consumer. Consumer behaviour means how individuals make decisions to spend their available resources like time, money, effort on consumption of different products and services. It includes what they buy, why they buy, the product and when they buy them, how often they buy and use it. This paper will analyse the perspective of consumer and their behaviour using Engel-Kollat-Blackwell model. This particular study is empirical in nature. It states how information technology models help us to find factors influencing consumers in buying a particular product. This IT model is briefly explained in this paper with the help of taking mobile phone as an example. This research work will help us in understanding different market segments and evolve strategies to effect penetration in these markets.

Keywords: consumer behaviour, marketers, IT models.

Introduction

Consumers make buying decisions every day for many types of purchases. As a marketer we study consumer behaviour to find what, where and how much they buy. However, learning about consumer behaviour isn't so easy because the answers we seek are locked deep within the minds of the consumer. We don't know what influences their purchases. Ninety-five percent of thoughts and emotions that drive our purchase occur in unconscious mind, which is without our awareness the consumer decision making is said to occur in black box. Marketers absorb stimuli to which the consumer is exposed to, such as advertising and the response that an individual makes. The central question for marketers is how consumer will respond to various marketing actions a company might take. This paper presentation mainly focuses on how the consumer behaviour is evaluated with the help of IT models.

Factors Influencing Consumer Behavior

To fully understand how consumer behaviour affects marketing, it is essential to know the factors and how it affects.

Psychological Factors

Buying behaviour of individual depends upon his mindset and need at the point of time. The psychological factors include motivation,

learning, beliefs and attitude. These factors cannot be measured and valued because these are internal emotion but has a huge impact on consumer behaviour towards the product. As a marketer, the consumer requirements are to be measured with the help of knowing what they prefer, how they prefer and in what form they prefer.

Personal Factors

Personal factors affect individuals buying decision. This factors depends upon individual traits which includes his personality, self actualization needs, age etc. Besides this, his education also forms apart of personal factors. Since India has diversified cultural practices and customs which lead to differences in tastes and preferences to the life style they belong to.

Social Factors

Social factors are those factors which affects the consumer behaviour through their response towards their product, brand and company. These factors are influenced mainly by family, roles and statuses. Apart from the social background they belong to, the income level of the consumer also constitutes major part. It is mainly because the preferences and needs of rich and poor is different. In marketers point of view they have to analyze these factors of their target market so as to satisfy their needs efficiently and effectively.

Engel- Kollat-Blackwell Model

Engel kollat Blackwell model also referred as EKB model was proposed to analyse the decision making process of a consumer and the factors that influence him to buy that product. It was first developed in 1968; it is a conscious problem solving and learning model. It involves four components.

- Information processing
- Decision processing
- Decisional variables
- External factors

Information Processing

Information processing is a mechanism through which learning occurs. Just like a computer the human mind takes in information, organizes and stores it to be retrieved at a later time. The consumer acknowledges himself about that product through the exposure, attention, comprehension, acceptance and retention. Thereafter he will interpret and comprehendit.

Decision Processing

Decision making is a process of identifying and choosing alternatives based on the values, preferences and their beliefs. At first the consumer will recognize the problem and will research to find a best alternative. His choice of purchase will result in an action which may or may not satisfy him.

Decisional variable

Decision variables are the sub component that influences a consumer to make decisions on buying a product. It is a set of quantities that has to be determined in order to solve the problem. The decisional variables include believes, motives, attitude, lifestyle, intentions, evaluative criteria and the normative compliance.

External Factors

What a consumer buys and why he wants buy are mostly influence by their culture, values, their family and their social environment. People always wish to be social will make decisions that will

increase their social standard and esteem. Some decisions will also be influenced by unexpected circumstances, norms, reference groups, and family influences. These components collectively called as the external factors.

Research Objectives

In this study we propose the elements that influence the consumer to buy a product using ENGEL-KOLLAT-BLACKWELL model.

Scope of the Study

- To help the marketing companies by finding out the components that influences consumer to buy a product.
- To help manufacturers to make changes in their products accordingly.
- To find out which element plays the key role in influencing the consumers.
- To analyse consumer behaviour using EKB model since it is the most effective IT model.
- To find out the consumer preferences.

Research Methodology

Method of Data Collection

A questionnaire was prepared for the primary data. Multiple choices were given below the questions that are frames relevant to the topic. A sample size of 100 respondents has been used for this research. Data was analysed by simple mathematics called percentages. And the responses of the respondents are given below through graphical pie charts.

Findings and Analysis

Question: Gender

Question: Age Group

Question: Income Per Month

Question: How Long You Have Been Using this Phone

Question: What do you Like about the Brand You Chose Above?

Question: Where did you See the Mobile Advertisement

Findings

Findings were drawn by analysing the responses obtained from the questionnaire with consideration of Engel-Kollat-Blackwell model.

- Income plays important role in buying a product (mobile phones).
- Age is directly proportional to the usage span of the product (mobile phones). Young consumers will use for a shorter span unlike other consumers.
- Quality plays a vital role in decision of the consumer to buy a product
- Majority of the consumers acknowledge themselves about the product through online advertisements.
- Working people buy more products when compared to non-working people.

Conclusion

Consumer behaviour is comparatively a new field of study in marketing. All marketing decisions are based on the assumption of consumer behaviour. The Engel-Kollat-Blackwell model is the most effective IT model. It helps in problem recognition, information research, alternative evaluation, choices and to find the outcomes. It has a good description of active information seeking.